

ISic0755

I.Sicily inscription 0755

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Acate

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175793

EDCS 6100286

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0343b

Lavore, V. 1982. Un'epigrafe romana nel territorio di Acate. Comune di Acate, Ente provincial del Turismo, Ragusa.

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 185-186 no.69 fig.74

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0755. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385222>